

THE FAUNA OF FREE-LIVING TERRESTRIAL NEMATODES OF THE ARGENTINE ISLANDS

S. Susulovska¹, S. Glotov^{2,3,4}, A. Susulovsky²

¹Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Lviv, Ukraine;

²State Museum of Natural History, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Lviv, Ukraine; susulovsky@gmail.com;

³Lugansk Nature Reserve, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Stanytsia Luhanska, Ukraine;

⁴Luhansk Taras Shevchenko National University, Poltava, Ukraine

Nematodes are one of the richest and most abundant groups of terrestrial fauna in Antarctica. Around sixty terrestrial nematode species are currently reported to occur in Antarctica, representing 16 families and almost 30 genera.

The nematode fauna of Antarctica is clearly distinct from that of other continents. At least 90% of species currently known, and possibly approaching 100%, are endemic to the continent or smaller regions within it, indicating a long evolutionary history in isolation within the continent, as is now known to be characteristic of most Antarctic terrestrial fauna.

During the 27th Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition, 89 substrate samples were collected from the bird nests (south polar skua (*Stercorarius maccormicki*) and kelp gull (*Larus dominicanus*)) and moss clumps on the Galindez Island and nearby islands and rocks of the Wilhelm Archipelago such as Berthelot, Winter, Grotto, Indicator, Petermann, Skua, Hovgaard, Irizar, Central Pig, Eastern Pig, and Three Little Pigs Islands.

In total, more than 1260 nematode specimens were analyzed, and 430 of them were mounted on the permanent slides for the detailed morphological study.

The processing of these materials complements existing data on the distribution of nematodes in the Antarctic region, as samples were taken on 10 islands and two rocks where no nematological studies had been conducted previously.

The analysis of the collected materials revealed 23 species of free-living soil nematodes belonging to 13 genera, 11 families, and 6 orders for the Argentine Islands. Sixteen species were recorded in this region for the first time. The taxonomic diversity of nematodes of the Argentine Islands was revealed to be relatively high as it includes more than half of the species and genera reported for the entire Antarctic Maritime Region. The data on the nematode fauna of the region was complemented, as 16 identified species were reported for the first time for this sector of the Antarctic.

The most taxonomically diverse were bacteriophages of the genus *Plectus* (5 species). The order Dorylaimida was represented by five genera, among which *Eudorylaimus* (4 species) and *Mesodorylaimus* (3 species) had the largest number of species.

The chorological analysis of the collected material revealed that three genera (*Pararhysocolpus*, *Amblydorylaimus*, and *Enchodeloides*) and the majority of the identified species are endemic to Antarctica. Only two species of Monchysterida nematodes, namely *Eumonhystera vulgaris* and *Geomonhystera villosa*, are widespread outside the continent.

The nematode fauna of Galindez Island turned out to be the most abundant, with 13 species identified, and together with literature data, 15 species are currently known. It comprises about half of the fauna of the most thoroughly studied Antarctic islands – Livingstone (31 species) and King George (28 species) – parts of the South Shetland Archipelago. On a number of other islands, in particular, Winter, Petermann, Skua, Hovgaard, and Central Pig, 7–8 species were collected. However, at this

stage of research, the difference in the data for individual islands reflects the amount of high-quality material suitable for accurate identification rather than real differences in fauna.

Among the processed material, there are a number of populations, particularly in the genus *Mesodorylaimus*, that cannot be accurately identified and require further detailed morphological analysis.